

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

TRUST IS AN ECOSYSTEM

FOSTERING TRUST IN SCIENCE THROUGH SUPPORTIVE POLICY FRAMEWORKS

CALL: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44 -

TOPIC: SOCIETAL TRUST IN SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

PROJECT: VERITY

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WHY TRUST IN SCIENCE MATTERS FOR POLICY

Effective policymaking relies on a strong science-society relationship. Public trust in science is crucial for promoting scientific progress, strengthening democratic institutions, and enabling informed decision-making. While overall trust in science remains high across the EU and globally, challenges persist in translating this trust into public acceptance of policies grounded in scientific knowledge. [The VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science](#) offer actionable strategies to **support policymakers, as core Stewards of Trust**, in bridging science, society, and governance through a robust **ecosystem of trust in science**.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The trust in science ecosystem is becoming increasingly complex, influenced by a wide range of **actors** and **factors**. Scientific research is becoming more global and collaborative, particularly through digital and AI-driven methods. As a result, traditional conceptions of trust in science, once rooted in institutional accountability and centralised expert authority, are no longer sufficient. The shift from institutional trust to **distributed trust**, driven by social media, citizen science, public-private partnerships and private companies' involvement, has diversified the actors and networks involved in trust-building as Stewards of Trust. **Stewards of Trust** are organisations, groups, or individuals with expertise and commitment to strengthening trust in science. Their role may stem from an official mandate and mission or from their *de facto* power and influence. Therefore, **the ecosystem of trust in science is a dynamic space where trust is constructed, negotiated, enhanced or reduced**.

Current frameworks often fail to capture the complex interplay between emerging Stewards of Trust, a rapidly evolving research landscape, and the influence of social media, mis/disinformation, and technology such as AI. While science has gained visibility in policymaking, public trust in science-informed governance remains fragile and **undermined by politicisation and privatisation of science, short political cycles, limited institutional capacity, and lack of transparency**.

As Stewards of Trust, policymakers play a crucial role in shaping a research and innovation (R&I) system that is not only competitive globally but also open, responsible, and aligned with society. In light of the EU's renewed focus on competitiveness (e.g. Draghi report), **public investment in R&I must deliver both economic returns and tangible benefits for citizens**. This requires addressing grand challenges and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through inclusive, ethical, and human rights-based approaches.

POLICY RESULTS

As Stewards of Trust, policymakers play a key role in fostering trust in science by **embedding scientific integrity, transparency, and openness** into policy frameworks. This includes protecting the autonomy of public research institutions, **aligning research agendas with societal needs and SDGs**, and ensuring stable, unbiased funding. Trust-building also requires inclusive, long-term engagement strategies that involve citizens, researchers, and civil society in co-creating solutions, backed by mechanisms for fair compensation and meaningful participation. Investing in science-policy interfaces, improving coordination across departments and sectors, and supporting transparent communication about evidence, uncertainty, and ethical trade-offs are critical steps toward more trusted, democratic, and evidence-informed governance.

ECOSYSTEM OF TRUST

IN SCIENCE

The EU-funded VERITY project identifies the urgent need for redefining and fostering the **Ecosystem of Trust in Science** through a systemic approach. To address this challenge, it developed a [Protocol of Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science](#) that offers actionable strategies and practical **tools** for **Stewards of Trust**, who mediate between science and society. Grounded in well-established conceptual frameworks, comprehensive empirical research, and co-creation and validation processes with the active participation of more than 500 stakeholders, VERITY is positioned to provide robust and adaptable recommendations for guiding trust in science and strengthening collaboration between science and society.

6 KEY STRATEGIES FOR FOSTERING TRUST IN SCIENCE

Building Trustworthy Science

Trustworthy Science

- Promote alignment with high standards of scientific excellence, ethics and research integrity, and delivery of tangible societal benefits, collaborative practices, and open access to scientific knowledge.
- Improve transparency on funding sources and enhance independent research validation.

Engaging the Public in Scientific Processes

Public Engagement in Scientific Processes

- Institutionalise mechanisms for meaningful citizen involvement as co-creators in research, from design to implementation.
- Promote mutual understanding between researchers and society through inclusivity, fair recognition of public contributions and shared ownership of scientific progress.

Educating and Raising Awareness

Education & Awareness Raising

- Integrate digital literacy and critical thinking skills into formal education to address scientific complexity, uncertainty, and falsifiability, counter mis/disinformation, reduce echo chambers, and promote exposure to credible information.
- Extend science education and awareness-raising to all actors, including policymakers and media.

Science Communication

Science Communication

- Promote science communication that goes beyond transmitting facts to foster dialogue, relationships, and critical thinking.
- Ensure accessible, inclusive, and crisis-ready science communication strategies that counter mis/disinformation and foster public dialogue.
- Reform academic incentives to reward science communication and invest in communication infrastructure and training.

Building Supportive Policy Frameworks

Supportive Policy Frameworks

- Design science-informed policies that prioritise benefit sharing, transparency, inclusivity, and accountability.
- Avoid selective use of science to support short-term political agendas.

COLLABORATION

Cross-sector Collaboration

- Create mechanisms for interdisciplinary, international, and multi-stakeholder collaboration between Stewards of Trust, including science producers, educators, communicators, policymakers, funders, implementers, oversight and protection actors, and science-society facilitators.
- Foster a coordinated, innovative, and impactful science ecosystem built on trust and mutual benefit.

Trust in science is not static or one-dimensional but the result of a dynamic process within the ecosystem of trust. It emerges through the interactions of diverse Stewards of Trust, who shape it collectively rather than in isolation. Collaboration between all stakeholders is essential for implementing the key strategies and fostering public trust.

CALL TO ACTION

To strengthen societal trust in science and ensure effective governance, we urge policymakers to engage with the [VERITY Protocol of Recommendations](#). By prioritising cross-sector collaboration, transparency, inclusivity, and evidence-informed decision-making, you can help bridge the gap between science and society. We encourage you to incorporate the project's actionable strategies into your policy and regulatory frameworks and support cross-sectoral collaborations to strengthen trust in science!

VERITY Project

The VERITY project, funded under Horizon Europe (2022-2025), addresses growing concerns about varying levels of public trust in science. It explores how trust is built, eroded, and maintained. VERITY developed a **Protocol of Recommendations** that provides practical, evidence-informed strategies to guide **Stewards of Trust**, such as policymakers, scientists, educators, communicators, oversight bodies, implementors and civil society, to foster trust across diverse societal contexts. The **Ecosystem of Trust in Science** approach in the VERITY project builds on systems theory to understand trust in science as a dynamic and interconnected entity. Trust in science is shaped not only by the integrity of scientific research but also by the broader societal, political, and economic factors that influence public perceptions. The ecosystem of trust conceptualises trust as a relational, temporary state that evolves through interactions between the public (trustees) and scientific actors (trustees) as Stewards of Trust.

QR Code for **VERITY Protocol of Recommendations** on Zenodo

Project information

Project full title: deVEloping scientific Research with ethIcs and inTegritY

Coordinator: TRILATERAL RESEARCH LIMITED (TRI IE)

Consortium: EUREC OFFICE GUG (EUREC), PANEPISTIMIO DYTIKIS ATTIKIS (UniWA), F6S, UCLAN CYPRUS LIMITED (UCLAN CY), ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH (ZSI)

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Further Reading: [VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science](#)

Further Information: [VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science: SCIENCE POLICYMAKERS](#)
[VERITY Interactive Online Tool](#)
[VERITY Scenario-Building Training for Effective Implementation of Recommendations](#)

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